

Vertical distribution and variability of soil organic carbon and CaCO₃ in deep Colluvisols modeled by hyperspectral imaging

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ABSTRACT

The acceleration of soil erosion in undulating landscapes due to human activities has led to a larger area of land being affected by intensive soil redistribution. Colluvisols, sedimentary soils formed on concave slope positions, are considered to be important indicators of soil-landscape processes and soil organic carbon pools. In this study, we investigated the effectiveness of hyperspectral imaging in visible and near-infrared range to assess the detailed variability (both vertical and within each colluvial layer and in-situ soil horizon) of soil organic carbon (SOC) and CaCO₃ concentrations in three deep Colluvisols developed on loess and located at different slope positions in southeast Czechia, and evaluate whether this in-detail mapped microvariability can be used as a proxy to assess the dynamics and history of colluvial sedimentation. A variety of nonlinear machine learning techniques such as cubist regression tree (Cubist), random forest (RF), support vector machine regression (SVMR) and one linear technique partial least square regression (PLSR) were compared to determine the most suitable model for the prediction of SOC and CaCO₃ content in each profile. The results showed that RF provided the best performance for both SOC ($R^2 = 0.75$) and CaCO₃ ($R^2 = 0.76$) contents. The maps depict significant differences in the vertical variability of the predicted properties in the profiles depending on the different intensity, form and period of sedimentation resulting from the slope position. The within-horizon/layer variability of SOC proves to be a suitable indicator of the character of deposition. High variability has been shown mainly in the medieval layers, where it reflects high-energy material redeposition, while low variability in the oldest and youngest parts of the profiles is probably associated with the type of deposited material and frequent pedoturbation, respectively. The within-horizon/layer variability of CaCO₃, on the other hand, is independent of the dynamics of deposition. The study showed that imaging spectroscopy is a suitable tool to capture the detailed pattern of the colluvial matrix and, with appropriate sampling and processing, is applicable even in very deep soil profiles.

1. Introduction

Human activities have led to increasing rates of erosion and deposition in undulating landscapes, resulting in a larger area of land being affected by soil redistribution processes (De Moor and Verstraeten, 2008; Kappler et al., 2019). Particularly in central Europe, soil erosion has been identified as a major threat in loess areas (Balontayová et al., 2024; Boardman and Poesen, 2006; Žížala et al., 2018). In this sense, the research on Colluvisols is crucial, as they are considered an important source of information for the study of soil-landscape processes,

particularly the intensity of soil erosion and environmental changes (Dotterweich, 2008; Scherer et al., 2021; Van Der Meij et al., 2019). Colluvisols are defined as recently formed and undeveloped sedimentary soils, mainly found in concave slope environments (Zádorová and Penížek, 2018). They reflect natural, social, and historical influences particularly in agricultural landscapes, and represent an important geoarchive for documenting the history of land management (Dotterweich, 2008; Kittel, 2014; Kühn et al., 2017; Miller and Juilleret, 2020; Poręba et al., 2015). Due to their considerable depth, they also act as reservoirs of soil organic carbon (SOC) in undulating landscapes

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(Chaopricha and Marín-Spiotta, 2014; Zádorová et al., 2015).

Colluvisols form as a result of the active redistribution of soil material within a slope system where pedogenesis is periodically interrupted by sedimentation of new soil material (Zádorová et al., 2023b). The stratigraphy, thickness and vertical distribution of soil properties within the Colluvisols profile are influenced by a variety of factors, including sedimentation dynamics, source material, terrain configuration and land management (Leopold and Völkel, 2007; Poręba et al., 2011; Zádorová et al., 2013). Colluvisols with a thickness of several meters and rich in organic matter occur in loess regions. They develop from humus-rich soils, mainly Chernozems (Adameková et al., 2021; Kasielke et al., 2019; Zádorová et al., 2013) and Luvisols (Gonnet et al., 2023; Kadereit et al., 2010). In addition to depositional processes, both vertical mixing of the material by ploughing and bioturbation (Van Der Meij et al., 2019) and vertical and lateral movement of different substances in the soil profile as a result of leaching, or redox conditions influence the variability and distribution of different soil properties in Colluvisols. The intensity of these post-depositional processes largely depends on the environmental conditions, the intensity of sedimentation and slope stability (Dreibrodt et al., 2013; Kühn et al., 2017; Zádorová et al., 2023a). A number of studies investigating Colluvisols have mainly focused on their stratigraphy, age and paleoenvironmental implications (e.g., Dreibrodt et al., 2020; Fuchs and Lang, 2009; Kappler et al., 2019; Kühn et al., 2017; Zádorová et al., 2023b) which have allowed the reconstruction of past phases of human activity and climate oscillations. However, much less is known about the detailed-scale spatial variability of soil properties within the colluvial soil profile, which is important to better understand the role of sedimentary and pedogenetic processes in a complex dynamic environment influenced by a range of natural and anthropogenic factors.

Conventional sampling techniques and laboratory-based soil analysis methods for determining soil properties are based on sampling discrete depth intervals or horizons and subsequent homogenization of the material, which reduces the vertical resolution of the information content as the soil sample information is averaged per depth interval (Blanco-Canqui et al., 2017). Correspondingly, homogenization of samples is important to overcome the microscale heterogeneity of the soil, but it implies a loss of information about the spatial variability of the distribution of soil properties within the sample, reduces the representativeness of the measurement with respect to actual field conditions and limits our understanding of soil as a complex matrix in the environment (Viscarra Rossel et al., 2017). It also leads to a loss of statistical power, the improvement of which requires a larger number of samples, increasing the cost and effort of sampling (Hobley et al., 2018). To overcome the loss of information and to study the spatial variability of soil properties in the soil profile, methods such as soil core sampling are a faster and less labor-intensive alternative used in soil sampling and soil properties assessment (Viscarra Rossel et al., 2017). Recently, non-destructive alternative techniques that are inexpensive and fast have been increasingly used to determine soil properties. The use of digital soil morphometrics and chemometrics as a collection of tools and techniques to measure and quantify soil profile attributes and spatial variation with the purpose of improving pedological understanding, has been recently advanced (Hartemink et al., 2020; Hartemink and Minasny, 2014; Jones and McBratney, 2016). In particular, soil spectroscopy, i.e. the study of the spectral signature of a soil material in relation to organic and mineral components of the soil (Nocita et al., 2015), has been used to describe the vertical distribution of soil properties (Doetterl et al., 2013; Viscarra Rossel et al., 2022, 2017). In the last two decades, the use of visible and near-infrared (VNIR) reflectance spectroscopy has gained much interest in soil science because it allows the quantification of several soil properties by their spectral response in a fast and inexpensive manner compared to conventional laboratory analysis (Bellon-Maurel and McBratney, 2011; Greenberg et al., 2022; Nocita et al., 2015; Wadoux et al., 2021). Therefore, VNIR spectroscopy has been used to effectively characterize soil properties, such as SOC (Angelopoulou

et al., 2020), clay content (Greenberg et al., 2022), iron oxides (Zhao et al., 2020), CaCO₃ (Mirzaei et al., 2022) and salinity (Chatrenour et al., 2023).

Laboratory-based hyperspectral imaging (HSI) in the visible and near infrared regions (VNIR: 400–2500 nm) has been used in soil analyses to provide information on the vertical and horizontal distribution of soil properties in the soil profile at the micro-scale (Hobley et al., 2018). One of the advantages of coupling HSI with VNIR spectroscopy is that, unlike VNIR spectroscopy, HSI provides high spatial and spectral information in a three-dimensional (3D) image at the pixel scale (Roudier et al., 2016). Each pixel in the hyperspectral image retrieves a continuous spectrum that can be used for further characterization and analysis of multiple soil properties within a single measurement (Xu et al., 2020). Currently, laboratory-based HSI in the VNIR region has been used to analyze soil properties (Guigue et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2021). Studies have focused mainly on soil profiles limited to the depths of 30 cm (Steffens and Buddenbaum, 2013), 50 cm (Schreiner et al., 2015) and 100 cm. For example, Wu et al. (2018) used a hyperspectral camera with a spectral range of 397–1018 nm to map salt content with a spatial resolution of 0.4 mm in a soil profile (0–100 cm). Xu et al. (2022) evaluated six Fe parameters using a hyperspectral camera with a spectral range of 400–1010 nm in a soil profile (0–100 cm). To date, only a few studies (Hobley et al., 2018; Sorenson et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2011) have been focused on predicting SOC content along deeper soil profiles (up to 100 cm) using laboratory-based HSI (396–1000 nm). To the best of our knowledge, there are no studies that have considered HSI in the VNIR region at greater depths of the soil profile (>100 cm). The assessment of such deep subsoils is particularly important mainly in the landscapes affected by soil material redistribution with alterations of in-situ soils, soil sediments and buried soils. Due to the function of colluvial soils as a considerable reservoir of organic carbon in the landscape (Zádorová et al., 2015), the possibility of a detailed determination of the vertical distribution of SOC in deep profiles allows for a more accurate quantification of the amount of organic matter bound in these soils.

In this study, we investigated the vertical variability and the variability within each in-situ soil horizon or colluvial layer (within-horizon/layer variability) of SOC and CaCO₃ in deep Colluvisol profiles to identify the differences corresponding to terrain position and character of material deposition using laboratory HSI in the VNIR spectral region. We assume that, due to its high resolution, HSI in the VNIR region can capture the fine scale spatial variability of spectral properties throughout the profile, providing valuable information on soil properties distribution and dynamics of the material accumulation. Our objectives were to i) evaluate the suitability of using HSI in the VNIR spectral region to derive maps of SOC and CaCO₃ for investigating spatial patterns and variability of these soil properties, ii) to assess the detailed vertical and within-horizon/layer variability of the distribution of soil properties in the studied profiles, iii) and to relate the variability of soil properties to the sedimentation patterns in the study area.

2. Regional settings

The study plot (Fig. 1) is located in the cadaster of Brumovice municipality (48.967 °N, 16.882 °E) in Southern Moravia (SE Czechia). Climatically, the region belongs to the warmest and driest areas in Czechia. According to the data from the nearest measuring stations of the Czech Hydrometeorological Institute, the average rainfall between 1961 and 2021 was 511 mm/year and the average temperature was 9.5 °C. The site is located in the geomorphological region of the Central Moravian Carpathians, specifically the Ždánický les, an undulating upland with a mean altitude of 271 m above sea level. The area consists mainly of Paleogene sediments of the Outer Carpathian nappes (Eocene and Oligocene sandstones, associated with marls, clays and conglomerates), overlain by layers of Pleistocene loess and loess-like sediments of various thicknesses (Chlupáč, 2002). The region is strongly affected

Fig. 1. Localization of the study plot and sampled profiles (A), the distribution of agricultural parcels in 1950 s (B) and shaded relief (C). Source: CUZK – orthophoto map and Digital Relief Model of the Czech Republic 4th generation (DRM4G).

by soil erosion and the soil cover is formed by a mosaic of originally dominant Chernozems, Regosols and Calcisols, resulting from the truncation of former profiles, and deep colluvial soils with often several meters thick layers of redeposited soil material, forming the natural sinks of soil organic carbon (Zádorová et al., 2015). The study plot consists of a six-hectare section of a larger agricultural parcel under long-term conventional tillage. It is a partially closed slope system comprising several types of terrain units. Calcic Chernozems (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022) cover the flat plateau in the southern part of the plot, while the side valley leading into a large colluvial-alluvial cone represents the most prominent colluvial positions with deep Colluvisols (Haplic and Chernic Phaeozems (Solimovic) and Solimovic Regosols). The adjacent back-slopes (slopes up to 19°) are heavily eroded with truncated soil profiles (Haplic Calcisols) where loess substrate is incorporated into the topsoil.

The wider area with the regional center of Břeclav has been under continuous agricultural use since the Neolithic (Koštuřík and Unger, 1977), although the study plot is rather distant from this center of settlement, and it is possible to assume later colonization. The main anthropogenic pressure, based on the dating of the colluvial sediments at the study plot (Zádorová et al., 2023b), was determined in the periods of the Early and Middle Bronze Age, the Iron Age and especially in the High and Late Middle Ages and after 1950. The oldest colluvial layers in the overburden of the original in-situ profiles have been dated to the Early (side valley) and Late Neolithic (toe-slope) periods, respectively. For a detailed description of the soil cover and history of erosion–deposition processes at the plot, see Zádorová et al. (2023a,b).

3. Methods

3.1. Field sampling and samples preparation

The three analyzed profiles were located on the toe-slope (P1 and P2) and side valley (P3), representing the areas of the most intense material deposition on the plot. The profiles were cored from the surface down to

the parent material using a percussion drill kit. The percussion drill down to a depth of 100 cm has a diameter of 100 mm. At greater depths, the percussion drill's diameter changes to 75 mm. Sampling points were pre-selected based on several detailed surveys conducted at the site in previous years. A network of 600 gouge-auger probes taken in a regular network (Zádorová et al., 2011) was available, as well as an irregular network of 3–5 m deep drilled cores (Zádorová et al., 2015). The exact location of the sampling points was further refined in the field by 5 additional cores drilled at the pre-selected locations.

The undisturbed sections of the profile were removed from the drill rods in the foil liners and taken to the laboratory, where they were placed in plastic half pipes of appropriate diameter. To prepare the soil profiles for hyperspectral image analysis, the cores were placed horizontally and carefully cut in half from top to bottom with a knife. Care was taken to avoid contamination and smearing during the cutting. The intact half-section soil core was air dried at room temperature and reserved for hyperspectral imaging.

3.2. Hyperspectral image acquisition

The prepared soil cores were scanned using a laboratory setup with a hyperspectral imaging system, after automatic dark background correction. The system consisted of the following four components i) an A-series hyperspectral VNIR camera coupled to an imaging spectrograph (Hypspec VNIR-1800 camera, Norsk Elektro Optikk, Norway); ii) two 150 W halogen lamps for illumination; iii) a customized moving sample stage driven by a stepper motor (Hypspec); iv) a computer with spectral image software (HySpex v3.1). The instruments were operated in a dark chamber to minimize the ambient light effects during the sample scanning. The half-section soil profile was placed on the sample stage and was moved into the field of view of the camera. The camera was fitted with a 30 cm lens with 1800 detectors in-line and a field of view of ~ 10 cm (final spatial resolution of image ~ 53 × 53 μm² per pixel). For each pixel, 186 bands in the region 400–1000 nm were obtained at a spectral resolution of 3.17 nm. The cores were mounted on a push broom

translation stage that was moved under the camera and two 150 W illumination lamps during the scan acquisition. The HSI images were calibrated using both white and black correction (Norsk Elektro Optikk, 2014). Prior to sample image acquisition, a reference scan of a calibration target with defined reflectance (~50 %) was captured by using a Zenith Polymer (SphereOptics), which is a material providing diffuse reflectance across a wide wavelength range (250 to 2450 nm). The black correction was performed by capturing dark frames (with no light) to subtract dark current and electronic noise from the raw data, ensuring accurate measurements. The system automatically does this when the shutter is closed and an average of 200 dark frames is acquired.

Background, plastic pipe, light overexposure, and shadows were later masked using ENVI version 5.2 (Exelis Visual Information Solutions, Boulder, CO) by mapping the spectral intensity of the VNIR band at 980 nm and the ratios of the spectral intensity of bands at 980 and 420 nm, and of bands at 630 nm and 420 nm. Thresholds in the spectral response and ratios were identified and used to mask non-soil components of the images. The imaging spectrometer was calibrated by the manufacturer.

3.3. Image pre-processing and sampling in the soil cores

The preprocessing was done in two steps: first, the noisy parts of spectra between 400 and 500 nm, as well as 900 and 1000 nm, were removed (Wadoux et al., 2021). Spectra between 500 and 900 nm were kept. Second, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed to identify fine-scale qualitative differences in the spectral properties of the profiles. Spectrally distinct regions were identified at all depths, based on score projections of the PCA first three components of the 186 bands in the VNIR spectra. These regions, along with visually identified differences in soil core surface properties, were used to select homogeneous regions of interest (ROIs) that were used to sample the variability in each profile by horizon/layer, (e.g., a minimum of three ROIs for a 15 cm thick horizon/layer and a maximum of 14 ROIs for a 110 cm thick horizon/layer) and to extract the spectral information from the HSI images. Soil samples were carefully collected from the core surface by gently scratching the soil within each ROI using a microspatula. From each ROI, a sample weighing between 80 to 120 mg was collected, covering an area of $17.98 \pm 6.23 \text{ mm}^2$.

On average, the ROIs contain 10652 ± 7160 pixels. The spectral reflectance of each ROI was then extracted and averaged. In total, 71 ROIs in the profile 1 (P1), 26 in the profile 2 (P2) and 23 in the profile 3 (P3) were sampled and used to develop the calibration models. All the HSI images were preprocessed and analyzed using ENVI v5.3 (Exelis Visual Information Solutions, Boulder, CO, USA) and RStudio v4.3 (Terra package; Hijmans, 2020).

3.4. Soil analyses

The SOC content was determined by dry combustion method (ISO 10694:1995). SOC measurements were performed with a HEKATEch EuroEA 3000. Calibration was made against sulphanilamide ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$, 41.8 % C and 16.3 % N) and BBOT ($\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$, 72.5 % C and 6.5 % N). All measurements were performed with two analytical replicates. To determine the concentrations of total C (organic and inorganic), 20 mg of the sample in tin capsules was weighted. The concentration in organic C was obtained from a second measurement, 5 mg was weighed in silver capsules and 20 μL of 2 N HCl was added to destroy CaCO_3 . The samples were placed in an oven at 60 °C overnight. Finally, the samples in silver capsules were wrapped in tin capsules and measured for C concentrations. From the difference between total C and organic C, the inorganic C concentrations of the ROI sample was calculated. The CaCO_3 content is calculated by dividing the inorganic C concentrations by the molar mass of carbon and then multiplying by the molar mass of calcium carbonate. All measurements are expressed as percentages of the soil mass.

3.5. Model development

To quantify and map SOC and CaCO_3 , mathematical models were used to describe the relationship between spectral wavelengths and soil properties. Four modeling algorithms Cubist, Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR), Random Forest (RF) and Support Vector Machine Regression (SVMR) were tested for predictive modeling of SOC and CaCO_3 distribution using hyperspectral data. The models were run in R software using the caret package (Kuhn et al., 2023). As explained before (section 3.3), ROIs were used to sample the variability in each profile by horizon/layer. The models were built using the averaged spectral responses of each ROI of the three soil cores as predictor variables and the measured SOC and CaCO_3 as the response variables. Using the `caret::createDataPartition` function, the spectral data (SOC, CaCO_3 : 120 ROIs) were randomly split into a training (70 %) (SOC, CaCO_3 , $n = 84$), and a testing (30 %) (SOC, CaCO_3 , $n = 36$) subsets, ensuring an identical data distribution between both subsets via stratified random sampling. The training set was used by the models to learn relationships between the spectral data and soil properties, while the test samples were used to assess the predictive accuracy of the model.

In the `caret::train()` function, the method and hyperparameters were as follows: Cubist (method = 'cubist', committees, neighbours), PLRS (method = 'pls', ncomp), RF (method = 'rf', mtry, ntree), SVMR (method = 'svmRadial', sigma, C). For RF the number of trees (ntree) was set to 200. The hyperparameters were tuned 10 times in the training process using the `tuneLength()` function. The performance of the model is sensitive to the selection of parameters. In the caret package, the `caret::trainControl()` function was used to conduct a random search algorithm (Cubist, RF and SVMR), and grid search (PLSR, searched between 1 and 10). This involved performing 10 repetitions of 5-fold cross-validation (method = "repeatedcv") on the training set, enabling the acquisition of reliable and stable estimates while avoiding overfitting (Brus et al., 2011; Hengl and MacMillan, 2019). This cross-validation was applied to each machine learning model in each iteration consistently. For SOC and CaCO_3 the best model with the combination of parameter values was determined as the one with the lowest RMSE value (Table S1).

3.5.1. Model evaluation

The predictive performance and goodness-of-fit of the models were evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2), the root mean square error of prediction (RMSE), residual prediction deviation (RPD), and concordance correlation coefficient (CCC). The R^2 was calculated as the square of the correlation between the observed and predicted values. The RMSE was calculated as the mean prediction error (square root of the mean squared error). The RDP is defined as the standard deviation of the observed values divided by the RMSE. The RDP considers both prediction error and variation in observed values, resulting in a model validity metric that is objective and more easily comparable across model validation experiments (Williams and Sobering, 1993). The CCC combines precision and accuracy metrics to estimate how far the observed data deviate from the ideal concordance (Lin, 2000).

3.5.2. Predicting vertical distribution of SOC and CaCO_3 in soil profiles

Trained and tuned models were used to predict soil properties. To achieve this, the hypercube images, which are 3D data structures that include spatial (height and width) and spectral dimensions (wavelengths), were "unfolded" into a 2D matrix to facilitate the extraction of the spectral data for modeling. This restructuring was accomplished by "flattening" the image along its spatial dimensions, with each row in the matrix representing a single pixel and each band becoming a column vector. The matrix was used to apply the best multivariate model to predict the SOC and CaCO_3 content for each pixel of the hyperspectral images. The resulting matrix of the predicted values was used to generate a 2D image with the same dimensions as the original images, representing the fine spatial distribution of the soil properties.

3.6. Statistical analysis

Boxplots were created for each soil property to examine variation within and between soil horizons/layers. Individual plots were created for each property showing the median, quartiles, and any outliers within each horizon/layer. The relationship between the mean VNIR spectra of the colluvial profiles from different horizons/layers was tested using PCA. Coefficients of variation (CVs) by horizon/layer were calculated by dividing the standard deviation (SD) by the mean and were used to estimate the within-horizon/layer variation of the predicted SOC and CaCO₃. Variation was classified as low (CVs < 10 %), medium (CVs 10–20 %), or high (CVs ≥ 20 %).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Stratigraphy of the soil profiles

The stratigraphy and thickness of colluvial profiles vary significantly depending on their position in the slope system (Fig. 2). The most intense colluvial accumulation was observed in P1. P1 and P2 show distinct upper layers of humus-depleted, loess-like material, which are not present in the case of P3. Buried profiles of former surface Chernozems were found in the lower parts of the studied profiles. The profiles are classified according to the World Reference Base for Soil Resources (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022). Colluvial layers are designated as M (lat. *migrare*) according to Zádorová and Penížek (2018), in-situ developed soil horizons are designated according to the Guidelines for soil description (FAO, 2006).

The total depth of the colluvial profile P1, located in the western part of the colluvial-alluvial cone, is 570 cm. The stratification of the profile is visually pronounced, with well-identifiable boundaries between each colluvial layer and buried soil. The profile shows twelve morphologically distinct layers and horizons ranging in thickness from 15 to 110 cm, covering the former in-situ profile at a depth of 435 cm. The horizons/layers differ in color, SOC and CaCO₃ content. The upper part of the profile (0–270 cm), represented by Ap and colluvial layers M1–M4, is formed by pale colored (Munsell colors moist 10YR 4/3–5/2), strongly effervescent material. The profile becomes gradually darker (10YR 3/2 to 3/1) with moderate to no effervescence between 270 and 435 cm (M5–M8). The buried soil starting in 435 cm has a dark chernic horizon 2A_{hb} (10YR 2/1) that gradually transitions into brownish 2AC horizon (10YR 4/2); loess parent material was identified in 510 cm. The soil profile was classified as Solimovic Regosol (Siltic, Protocalcic) over Calcic Chernozem (Siltic).

The profile P2, Solimovic Regosol (Protocalcic, Siltic) over Calcic Chernozem (Siltic), is situated in the upper part of the dejection cone. It consists of eight morphologically different layers and horizons with thickness ranging between 15 and 90 cm. The original Chernozem profile was identified at a depth of 240 cm. The upper part of the profile (0–155 cm), represented by Ap, M1 and M2 is formed by light, strongly effervescent material (Munsell colour (moist) 10YR 4/4, resp. 10YR 3/4). M3 and M4 layers (155 and 240 cm) are significantly darker (10YR 3/3–10YR 2/2) and slightly to non-effervescent. The buried soil starting at 240 cm has a dark, non-effervescent chernic horizon 2A_{hb} (10YR 2/1) gradually transitioning into a brownish 2AC horizon. 3Ck calcareous parent material was identified in 280 cm.

The profile P3, Haplic Kastanozem (Solimovic, Siltic) over Calcic Chernozem (Siltic, Stagnic), is located in the upper part of the side valley. The profile shows the lowest thickness of the colluvial material and also less visually pronounced stratification. Seven layers and horizons were distinguished between 0 and 300 cm. The original buried soil is less discernible in the profile than in the other two profiles. The colors of the upper layers are markedly darker than in profiles P1 and P2, starting with lighter and slightly effervescent upper part (10YR 3/3 in 0–60 cm in Ap and M1), followed by dark non-effervescent layers M2 and M3 (60–180 cm; 10YR 3/2–10YR 2/1). The original chernic horizon

Fig. 2. Stratigraphy of the studied colluvial profiles (depth of horizons/layers' boundaries in cm) described in the field.

was identified at 215 cm, followed by weathered 2Bw (10YR 4/3). Geological substrate (calcareous clay) was identified at 275 cm.

In this study, the profiles resemble two types of Colluvisols as defined by Zádorová and Peňížek (2018): type A and B. The stratigraphy of profiles P1 and P2 is typical of the Colluvisol type A, which represents the advanced phase of the colluvial formation, characterized by a deep stratified soil profile mirroring the former undisturbed Chernozem. Indistinctive signs of post-depositional pedogenesis indicate that erosion–deposition processes exceeded soil formation and constituted a regression in soil development (Bajard et al., 2017). Similar profiles with a significant admixture of mineral material, eroded from the subsoil of truncated parent soils, in the upper layers have been observed in a

number of loess areas in Europe (e.g., Kadereit et al., 2010; Terhorst, 2000). They represent the late stages of material redistribution, particularly in areas of long-term agricultural use, resulting in gradual surface levelling (Juríková et al., 2022; Rodzik et al., 2014). Although colluvial profiles of considerable depth have been described (Dreibrodt et al., 2020, 2013; Kołodzyńska-Gawrysiak et al., 2018; Kühn et al., 2017; Scherer et al., 2023), the P1 profile is exceptional in the thickness of the sedimentary layers and even almost twice the depth of the studied and dated profile (Zádorová et al., 2023b), located at a distance of about 50 m on the toe slope. This indicates particularly intense sedimentation in this slope section, which probably represents the final part of the colluvial sediment transport pathway on the plot. A comparison of the

Fig. 3. Hyperspectral images of the soil cores. Left: true-color (RGB) image (red: 650 nm, green: 550 nm, blue: 450 nm). Right: PCA of hyperspectral images (RGB = 1st – 3rd PCA component). Regions of interest are indicated as yellow and red rectangles. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

depth and character of the material of profiles P1 and P2 with the previously dated colluvial profile mentioned above (Zádorová et al., 2023b), suggests that the approximately 180 cm (Ap-M2) of profile P1 and 70 cm (Ap-M1) of profile P2 correspond to sedimentation of the last 70 years. This is related to unprecedented changes in the parcel size and agricultural intensity during land collectivization (Lipský, 2001). The middle parts of profiles P1 (M3-M5, 180–330 cm) and P2 (M2, 70–155 cm) probably correspond to sediments of the High and Late Middle Ages (Zádorová et al., 2023b). The thickness of this layer, especially for P1 is consistent with the intensive development of settlements and agriculture in the area (Kordiovský, 1977), and with many evidences of colluvial deposition in Central Europe (Dotterweich, 2008). Concerning the lower, humus-rich layers (M6-M8 in P1, M3-M4 in P2), overlying the original surface, their deposition during the long interval between the Iron Age and the Late Neolithic can be assumed on the basis of the correlation with the reference profile. The stratigraphy of profile P3 is similar to Colluvisol type B characterized by a less stratified profile formed by erosion and deposition processes that have not resulted in intensive removal of soil materials (Zádorová and Penížek, 2018). According to the dated reference profile (Zádorová et al., 2023b), located in the side valley, older sedimentation predominated in this slope section, with a substantial representation of sediments from the Bronze Iron Ages and, in the upper part of the profile, from the High Middle Ages. The admixture of loess is only visible in the first 30 cm. Zádorová et al. (2023b) attributed this to the previous complete filling of the side valley and its current function as a transport pathway only, without significant sedimentation.

4.2. Soil spectral information at different horizons and layers

The PCA performed for each profile revealed fine-scale qualitative differences in the spectral properties between the individual horizons/layers in each profile. These spectral differences were the basis for the selection of ROIs along the profiles (Fig. 3; Table S2).

PCA was applied to the mean VNIR spectra of the Colluvisol profiles from different horizons/layers with different SOC and CaCO₃ contents (Fig. 4). The spectral reflectance showed differences among the horizon/layers. The first component summarizes about 90 % of the variation. In profile P1, the plough and the upper sedimentary layers (i.e., Ap-M3) were separated from the lower layers (M5-M8) and the buried Chernozem (2Ahb-2AC); the 2Ck horizon formed a separate group. Profile P2 followed a similar pattern where we identified four groups separating the upper layers (Ap-M2), the middle layers (M3-M4), the buried Chernozem (2Ahb-2AC) and the 2Ck horizon. Profile P3 shows three main groups distinguishing the plough layer (Ap) from the subsoil (M1-2Ahb) and the parent material (2Ck).

The fine-scale qualitative differences in the spectral properties between the top, middle and bottom parts of each soil profile were evident. Furthermore, spectral similarity was observed between neighboring layers. For example, the oldest colluvial layers (i.e., P1 = M8; P2 = M4; P3 = M3) and the buried in-situ Chernozem are formed by a high content of soil organic matter with low broad band albedo. At the same time, the parent material at the bottom of the profile exhibits high carbonate content and have high broadband albedo. Differences in soil spectra are influenced by the composition and distribution of soil properties (Dematté and Da Silva Terra, 2014; Zhao et al., 2020). Thus, we infer that SOC and CaCO₃ are significantly correlated with the soil spectra as validated by Terra et al. (2018). In our study, the soil spectral behaviors

Fig. 4. PCA for mean VNIR spectra of each horizon/layer by profile.

by horizon/layer vary distinctly in each landscape position due to modifications in soil physical, chemical and mineralogical properties induced by distinct sedimentary and pedogenetic processes that produced changes in the SOC and CaCO₃ content by horizon/layer. Organic matter interactions with the soil spectra were observed in the reduction of the reflectance intensity from 400 to 900 nm, confirmed by the oldest colluvial layers and the buried A horizon that showed low albedo and rectilinear and flat shape spectrum from 800 to approximately 1000 nm. Conversely, horizons/layers with high CaCO₃ content such as 2Ck are characterized by a higher albedo across the spectrum with an ascending shape between approximately 600 to 900 nm (Figs. S3.1, S3.2, S3.3).

4.3. Performance comparison of the calibration models for SOC and CaCO₃

To select the best predictive model for SOC and CaCO₃, different machine learning algorithms were compared based on four accuracy measures (Table 1). The results indicate that RF provided the best performance for SOC ($R^2 = 0.75$, RMSE = 0.30, RDP = 1.97, CCC = 0.84, bias = -0.07) and CaCO₃ ($R^2 = 0.76$, RMSE = 2.99, RDP = 2.03, CCC = 0.86, bias = -0.42). In contrast, the models with the lowest prediction performances for SOC and CaCO₃ were PLSR and SVMR, respectively. In general, the prediction accuracy for SOC and CaCO₃ was excellent ($0.80 < CCC \leq 0.9$).

A visual evaluation of the different algorithms was performed on the testing set using scatter plots (Fig. 5). Overall, the data points in all the SOC and CaCO₃ prediction models were closely distributed around their corresponding 1:1 line with narrow prediction intervals and low prediction errors. This modeling approach provided accurate predictions, with a high coefficient of determination ($R^2 > 0.7$).

In terms of the R^2 , RMSE, RDP, CCC and model bias metrics, the four tested multivariate models showed similar performance. The comparison suggested that the nonlinear models (i.e., Cubist, RF, SVMR) performed slightly better compared to the linear model (i.e., PLSR). RF produced the best calibration statistics for SOC and CaCO₃.

The RF model predictions were most similar to the distribution of SOC and CaCO₃ in terms of mean, median, min, max values and standard deviation (Table S4), indicating that the predicted values reflect the general distribution of SOC and CaCO₃ content. On the other hand, the poor goodness-of-fit statistics of Cubist and PLSR to predict SOC content and PLSR and SVMR to predict CaCO₃ indicate that the algorithms were unable to capture and reproduce the distribution and variability of these soil properties along the profiles. Even though the optimization was performed using cross-validation, the models were unable to reproduce reliable results making them unsuitable for predictive purposes.

The accurate identification of spectrally active soil components with VNIR spectroscopy depends on the selection of an adequate multivariate calibration technique (Viscarra Rossel and Behrens, 2010; Viscarra Rossel et al., 2022). We tested multivariate models to find a suitable approximation that describes the relationship between the VNIR

hyperspectral data and the concentrations of SOC and CaCO₃. This further enables the derivation of maps to investigate the spatial patterns and variability of these soil properties in each landscape position. Therefore, we assumed that the statistical methods that would perform most effectively are likely those that are best suited to the structure of the spectral data. For high-dimensional and multicollinear data, as used in our study, it should be expected that selecting models that deal effectively with collinearity may be advantageous. This could be achieved with the selection of PLSR, decomposing the data into a set of orthogonal variables that explain the variation, which are then used in a regression analysis of soil attributes (Dangal et al., 2019). Contrastingly, nonlinear models could identify nonlinear relations between SOC, CaCO₃ and hyperspectral data. Cubist partitions the data into rule-based segments, applying localized linear regressions to capture complex, nonlinear relationships (Quinlan, 1993). RF is a tree-based structure driven by stochastic processes, recursively partitioning a response variable into increasingly pure nodes based on the predictor variables (Breiman, 2001). Moreover, one of the advantages of RF is that it estimates the importance of each variable by analysing the prediction error when out of bag (OOB) data for a few variables is permuted while all others are left unchanged (Breiman, 2001). This allows identifying the relevant spectral regions and vibrational groups (De Santana et al., 2018). SVMR differs from the previous methods by condensing the number of training samples to a smaller subset of significant support vectors (Vapnik, 1995). Despite these conceptual differences, the four tested multivariate models showed similar performance. However, the complex soil spectral behaviors observed across horizons and landscape positions were better explained by RF, a nonlinear model. This is due to the modifications in soil physical, chemical, and mineralogical properties, which were induced by distinct sedimentary and pedogenetic processes that produced nonlinear changes in the SOC and CaCO₃ content across the horizons/layers.

There is a lack of applications in the literature using HSI in the VNIR region to develop and test multivariate models for predicting SOC and CaCO₃ contents for sediment-origin and deep soil profiles. The available applications in different soil types are limited to 1 m depth mostly focused on SOC and in the case of CaCO₃ using spectral signatures in the SWIR spectral region (Mathieu et al., 2017). This lack of applications in the VNIR region (400–1000 nm) makes comparison difficult; nonetheless, we present a comparison based on studies of HSI in the VNIR (400–1000 nm) region applied to soils of 1 m depth for SOC. In our study, the performance of the RF regression model for SOC ($R^2 = 0.75$, RMSE = 0.30), was significantly influenced by the spectral regions between 553 to 626 nm, with a lower influence from the spectral regions between 763 and 792 nm (Fig. S5.1). The 553 nm wavelength has been associated with iron minerals (Dematté and Da Silva Terra, 2014), while and 763 to 798 nm range has been linked to humic compounds and pigments derived from chlorophyll and phenolic compounds that are produced during the decomposition of organic matter and plant residues in the soil (Daughtry, 2001; Fidêncio et al., 2002). Similarly, Peng et al. (2024) collected eight soil cores in a mining reclamation site and used a mixed approach of HSI and point measurement of spectra. Then they trained the model using 65 samples. The highest accuracy using RF model ($R^2 = 0.94$, RMSE = 7.5 gkg⁻¹) was obtained, providing a successful prediction of SOC by horizon/layer. They detected a peak around 665 nm, associated with soil samples with low SOC and iron-containing minerals. Based on 66 samples extracted from a stagnic Luvisol profile, Steffens and Buddenbaum, (2013) trained PLSR ($R^2 = 0.81$, RMSE = 2.62) and SVMR ($R^2 = 0.97$, RMSE = 1.13) models, from which the latest yielded the best results. However, their results were constrained for the lack of independent training areas for the accurate model generalization. They identified a significant relation between SOC and the spectral range of 400 to 990 nm explained by the molecular vibrations involving C-H, N-H, and O-H bonds, iron oxides and the influence of texture impacting the light scattering. Xu et al. (2020), compared one linear (PLSR) and four nonlinear (artificial neural networks, Cubist,

Table 1
Predictive accuracy results of the different machine learning techniques.

Variable	Number of training samples	Model	Validation of test dataset (n = 36)				
			R ²	RMSE	RPD	CCC	bias
SOC	84	Cubist	0.66	0.35	1.68	0.80	-0.07
		PLSR	0.56	0.50	1.13	0.71	0.05
		RF	0.75	0.30	1.97	0.84	-0.07
		SVMR	0.74	0.30	1.97	0.84	-0.01
CaCO ₃	84	Cubist	0.72	2.82	1.91	0.84	0.44
		PLSR	0.70	3.33	1.70	0.83	0.57
		RF	0.76	2.99	2.03	0.86	-0.42
		SVMR	0.68	3.95	1.67	0.76	1.15

R²: coefficient of determination; RMSE: Root Mean Square Error; RPD: Residual Prediction Deviation; CCC: Concordance Correlation Coefficient.

Fig. 5. Scatter plots of observed versus HSI-modeled soil SOC and CaCO_3 parameters using different machine learning techniques in the testing set. The 1:1 line and the regression line are indicated in each figure. The grey-colored regions represent 95 % prediction confidence intervals.

Gaussian process regression, and SVMR) multivariate models. Among these, SVMR exhibited the highest prediction accuracies ($R^2 = 0.93$, $\text{RMSE} = 1.54 \text{ gkg}^{-1}$). The significant bands for SOC prediction were in the visible region (580–800 nm), which is mainly influenced by iron oxides and the color of the SOC itself. Similar to our study, Tahmasbian et al. (2018) used 120 SOC samples. In this case, PLSR model ($R^2 = 0.71$, $\text{RMSE} = 12.1$) was used, limiting the study to test only linear relationships between spectra and SOC laboratory data. The most important wavelengths were between 740 to 800 nm and 930 to 1000 nm linked to humic compounds and Chlorophyll-derived pigments reflecting the presence of organic residues. In our study, the CaCO_3 prediction ($R^2 = 0.76$, $\text{RMSE} = 2.99$) was significantly influenced by the spectral regions between 553 to 563 nm (Fig. S5.2). Distinct horizons/layers with high CaCO_3 content along the profile increased the light color of the soil. According to Ben-Dor and Banin (1994), since CaCO_3 does not have any absorption features in the VNIR spectral region, CaCO_3 is predicted based on the soil albedo or color in dry conditions. The application of HSI in the VNIR region to develop and test multivariate models for mapping CaCO_3 along the soil profile remains limited. Studies have documented the application of HSI in the VNIR region acquired from airborne or satellite platforms for prediction of CaCO_3 in the topsoil (Gomez et al., 2008; Lagacherie et al., 2008) or using VNIR spectroscopy as point reflectance with algorithms for prediction of CaCO_3 along the profile (Gomez and Coulouma, 2018; Karami et al., 2024; Mina et al., 2021; Ostovari et al., 2018).

Overall, the different studies raise the issue that spectral predictive multivariate models may vary in function of sample preparation, light scattering, spectral preprocessing and soil characteristics. In particular, the soil composition, influenced by distinct sedimentary and pedogenetic processes, affects the decomposition stage of organic matter, the nature of existing compounds, and the influence of factors like texture and iron oxides (Ben-Dor and Banin, 1994; Mouazen et al., 2007; Viscarra Rossel and Behrens, 2010). Given the complexity of soil variability, it is not possible to assign a single model for all cases. We advise against relying only on linear models for this application and instead encourage exploring multiple modelling approaches. Future applications of HSI coupled with multivariate models to map soil properties variability could integrate additional preprocessing techniques, explore wider spectral regions and include environmental covariates.

4.4. Predicted vertical distribution of SOC and CaCO_3 in soil profiles

In this study, the RF model was applied to HSI hypercubes to predict the SOC and CaCO_3 content in each soil profile at pixel level. The 2D false-color images exhibited concentration gradients and spatial distribution of SOC and CaCO_3 for the Colluvisol profiles at each landscape position (Figs. 6 and 7). To confirm the prediction results, the vertical distribution of each reference soil laboratory determination in ROI is also illustrated to the left of the corresponding map (base data shown in Table S2). The SOC and CaCO_3 maps, at the micrometer scale, depicted the horizontal and vertical characteristics of the soil profiles in detail. The transitions between horizons and layers in each profile were clearly distinguished from the profile prediction maps.

The soil profiles exhibited specific patterns in the concentrations of SOC and CaCO_3 (Fig. 8). There are some general trends in SOC content evident in all profiles, i.e. moderate SOC content in the upper part and an increase with depth. The maximum SOC content in all profiles was reached in the buried chernic horizon.

In P1 the SOC content shows a clear gradient with peaks in the lower part of the profile (Fig. 8a). The SOC content in the upper 270 cm (Ap-M4) is moderate and decreases with depth (means 1.07–1.01 %). Then the SOC gradually increases in the depth between 270–435 cm (M5-M8) to its maximum at 435 cm, in the 2Ahb horizon (mean 2.10 %). In P2 (Fig. 8b), the SOC shows lower concentrations in the upper part of the profile with the minimum in M2 (mean 1.01 %) and gradually increases towards 265 cm, where it peaks in 2Ahb horizon (mean 1.57 %). Profile P3 does not show such decrease in SOC content below the topsoil as the other two profiles, but a trend of increasing SOC with depth was also observed. The M3 layer has the highest SOC content (mean 1.89 %), while it is slightly lower in the buried in-situ chernic horizon (1.83 %).

The CaCO_3 content gradient is largely opposite to the SOC distribution in the profiles (Fig. 8). The highest values, except for the parent material, were identified in the upper parts of the profiles, mostly in topsoil and one or two layers below. In contrast, buried chernic horizons and the oldest sedimentary layers were either completely free of carbonate or contained minimal amounts in all profiles.

For the profile P1, the CaCO_3 content is higher in the upper 0–180 cm (Ap-M2) (means 12.41 % in Ap and 10.59 % in M2) and then gradually decreases with depth with a minimum in 2Ahb (mean 2.54 %). Profile

P1

Fig. 6. Predicted SOC and CaCO_3 content of the cored Colluvisol P1. Left: true-colour (RGB) image (red: 650 nm, green: 550 nm, blue: 450 nm). Centre: vertical distribution of laboratory-measured soil SOC, CaCO_3 content within the profile. Right: false colour image predicted SOC and CaCO_3 content. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

P2 shows a similar CaCO_3 concentration pattern to P1 with high concentrations in Ap-M2 (means 12.47 % in Ap and 9.60 % in M2) and a decrease towards the older parts of the profile (minimum mean 2.479 % in 2Ahb). Profile P3 shows moderate CaCO_3 content even in the plough layer (maximum mean 10.41 % in Ap). The concentration decreases rapidly in the subsoil with low values (means 2.55–2.04 %) between 60–215 cm (M2-M3).

The stratification is notably expressed in the vertical distribution of SOC and CaCO_3 content, indicating the mixture and accumulation of material from various sources. At profiles P1 and P2 the moderate SOC content and the high content of CaCO_3 in the upper half of the profiles, are due to the significant admixture of loess, which probably corresponds to the abrupt change in erosion intensity, truncation of the soils in the source area and predominant sedimentation of material from mineral subsoil. Given that this change occurs in layers probably corresponding to the High Middle Ages (Zádorová et al., 2023b), it may be related to both population pressure and extraordinary precipitation events during this period (Brázdil et al., 2011; Dotterweich, 2008). In contrast, the humus-rich and carbonate-poor lower parts of profiles P1

and P2, as well as most of profile P3, correspond to sedimentation from the A horizons of the source soils. A high proportion of SOC in the oldest sedimentary layers can be attributed to the selective transport of organic material during the first stage of colluviation (Heckrath et al., 2005) or ongoing bioaccumulation after the deposition (Zádorová et al., 2023a). Pavlů et al. (2023) also identified the most stable organic matter in this position, which may indicate a strong affinity for mineral substances such as iron or fine textural particles and thus a reduced decomposition rate (Kögel-Knabner et al., 2008).

4.5. Predicted within-horizon/layer variability of SOC and CaCO_3 in soil profiles

Fig. 9 shows the variability of SOC and CaCO_3 contents within individual horizons and colluvial layers. The assessment of within-horizon/layer variability was based on the analysis of all predicted values. Assessment based on observed analytical values is problematic because, especially for thin horizons, the problem of insufficient number of samples for variability evaluation arises. In general, it can be assumed

Fig. 7. Predicted SOC and CaCO_3 content of the cored Colluvisol P2 and P3. Left: true-colour (RGB) image (red: 650 nm, green: 550 nm, blue: 450 nm). Centre: vertical distribution of laboratory-measured soil SOC, CaCO_3 content within the profile. Right: false colour image predicted SOC and CaCO_3 content. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

that the within-horizon/layer variability can be attributed to the type and intensity of sedimentation at different periods of the profile up-building, which is reflected in the character of the accumulated material (Poręba et al., 2011). However, there are other factors that may affect the quality of this information: i) the thickness of the horizon/layers, ii) values of the individual properties, e.g., the influence of very low values on the variability; iii) the subjective division of the profile into different horizons/layers based on morphometric properties that may not correspond completely with the different periods of sedimentation, iv) possible contamination during sampling, which, despite efforts to limit it as much as possible, cannot be excluded. SOC variability follows a similar trend across all profiles. The variability does not depend on the thickness of the horizons/layers or on the mean value of SOC content (correlation coefficient = 0.11, resp. -0.17). The lowest variability (CV 10–20 %) was identified in two positions, firstly in buried chernic horizons and the oldest colluvial layers (P1 M8, P2 M4, P3 M3), and secondly in topsoil and layers corresponding to recent sedimentation (P1 M1-M2, P2 M2). In contrast, higher variability was present in all profiles in layers presumably corresponding to medieval sedimentation. The homogeneous distribution of SOC in Ap can be expected due to mixing of material by ploughing. In the case of the in-situ chernic horizons, the lower variability is associated with a stable contribution of organic matter from the original, probably steppe or forest-steppe vegetation

(Lang and Bork, 2006), as well as with intensive activity of the soil fauna (Zádorová et al., 2023a), while in the oldest sedimentary layers, the overall calmer sedimentation of the material eroded exclusively from the A horizons seems to be reflected. In addition, it is possible to consider continued pedogenesis and, similarly to the buried in-situ chernic horizon, an intensive bioturbation, because the deposition of the oldest layers was probably followed by a longer period of slope stability (Zádorová et al., 2023b). Rather surprising is the low SOC variability in the youngest layers, corresponding to the last 70 years. In general, an intense dynamics of material redistribution is expected during this period, with deposition of thick layers after intense precipitation events (e.g., Clemens and Stahr, 1994; Kadereit et al., 2010; Poręba et al., 2011). This rapid, often rill erosion, tends to favor deposition of material from different parts of the source profiles, i.e. topsoil and subsoil. The low variability may thus be due both to the complete depletion of the source profiles, where the ploughing of the loess subsoil makes the entire profile nearly homogeneous, and to the frequent and relatively deep ploughing of each newly deposited sedimentary layer. The higher variability in SOC content in the medieval layers can be attributed to a sudden shift in erosional intensity. Due to the increase in population pressure in the area, land clearance, more intensive cultivation (Beranová and Kubačák, 2010) and intense rainfall episodes, there may have been a change in the character of erosion, from the

Fig. 8. Boxplots showing within- and between-horizon/layer variation of SOC and CaCO₃ in three profiles at different landscape positions. Individual boxplots show the median, quartiles and outliers within each horizon/layer.

previous predominant sheet erosion, preferentially transporting material from the topsoil, to rill erosion, affecting the lower parts of the source profiles. This would therefore result in the transport of different types of material and an increase in the variability of deposited sediments. Such intense erosion and a tendency to gully is shown by a number of sedimentary records in Central Europe (Dotterweich, 2008; Dreibrodt et al., 2013; Henkner et al., 2018).

Variability in calcium carbonate content is generally higher with peaks in older layers and in-situ horizons (up to 70 %) and layers and lowest in topsoil and parent material (20–30 %). In contrast to SOC, the variability of CaCO₃ is significantly correlated with calcium carbonate concentration (correlation coefficient = -0.93), with horizons and layers with minimal CaCO₃ reaching the highest values. Here, the high variability is most likely caused by very small deviations in the predicted

values and thus a direct relationship between variability and the deposition type cannot be assumed.

5. Conclusion

This study evaluates the variability of soil properties in three Col-luvisol profiles at different landscape positions. This is the first attempt to evaluate the suitability of HSI spectroscopy in the VNIR region to map SOC and CaCO₃ distribution to investigate its variability in deep Col-luvisols and relate it with the specific sedimentation patterns forming the colluvial profiles.

Our results show that the coupling of HSI in the VNIR region with machine learning can be successfully applied to the high-resolution mapping of SOC and CaCO₃ content in deep soil profiles. The detailed

Fig. 9. Within-horizon/layer variability of SOC and CaCO_3 concentrations based on predicted values (CV – coefficient of variation).

representation of SOC and CaCO_3 gradients and their variability throughout the profile not only shows the precise spatial distribution of these properties, further applicable in various digital soil mapping-oriented applications but is also a useful tool for identifying distinct soil forming phases associated to the character of sedimentation dynamics, source material, terrain configuration and land management characteristics of each landscape position. A major advantage of this approach was the detailed capture of the spatial variability of the investigated properties. This is limited by the mixing of samples in classical sampling. In particular, the within-horizon/layer variability of SOC provided a good indicator of sedimentation dynamics at different positions.

Future applications of this approach should focus on increasing the number of samples to reconstruct broader patterns of sedimentation history in the erosion-prone landscapes. In addition, the challenges associated with potential contamination during sampling, sample preparation and the subjective division of the profile into different horizons layers based on morphometric properties that may not fully correspond to the different periods of sedimentation need to be addressed and improved. In future studies, it is necessary to explore wider regions of the electromagnetic spectrum to capture other soil properties that will allow for a comprehensive study leading to a more robust estimation of the erosion and sedimentation history in deep Colluvisol profiles.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jessica Reyes-Rojas: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Julien Guigue:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Daniel Žížala:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Vít Penížek:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation. **Tomáš Hrdlička:** Investigation. **Petra Vokurková:** Investigation. **Aleš Vaněk:** Investigation. **Tereza Zádorová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2024.117146>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14274809>.

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